

Improving remote estimation of winter crops gross ecosystem production by inclusion of leaf area index in a spectral model

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ABSTRACT

The hysteresis of the seasonal relationships between vegetation indices (*VI*s) and gross ecosystem production (*GEP*) results in differences between these relationships during vegetative and reproductive phases of plant development cycle and may limit their applicability for estimation of croplands productivity over the entire season. To mitigate this problem and to increase the accuracy of remote sensing-based models for *GEP* estimation we developed a simple empirical model where greenness-related *VI*s are multiplied by the leaf area index (*LAI*). The product of this multiplication has the same seasonality as *GEP*, and specifically for vegetative periods of winter crops, it allowed the accuracy of *GEP* estimations to increase and resulted in a significant reduction of the hysteresis of *VI*s vs. *GEP*. Our objective was to test the multiyear relationships between *VI*s and daily *GEP* in order to develop more general models maintaining reliable performance when applied to years characterized by different climatic conditions. The general model parametrized with *NDVI* and *LAI* product allowed to estimate daily *GEP* of winter and spring crops with an error smaller than 14%, and the rate of *GEP* over- (for spring barley) or underestimation (for winter crops and potato) was smaller than 25%. The proposed approach may increase the accuracy of crop productivity estimation when greenness *VI*s are saturating early in the growing season.

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INTRODUCTION

Leaf area index (*LAI*) as well as parameters describing carbon dioxide (CO_2) exchange between plants and the atmosphere such as net ecosystem production (*NEP*) and gross ecosystem production (*GEP*) are key biophysical parameters, which are commonly applied to qualitatively and quantitatively characterize the status of vegetation canopies. Numerous studies have confirmed that based on *LAI* the intensity of photosynthesis, transpiration, and productivity of plants might be assessed (*Borge & Leblanc, 2001; Breda, 2003; Zarco-Tejada, Ustin & Whiting, 2005*). Hence, *LAI* can be used as a proxy of plant growth, biomass and yield, as well as carbon dioxide fluxes exchanged between the ecosystem

and the atmosphere (Breda, 2003; Glenn *et al.*, 2008). *GEP* reflects the total amount of CO₂ assimilated by plants in photosynthesis (Waring, Landsberg & Williams, 1998). It depends on the amount, type and physiological condition of plants, but also on climate and habitat conditions (Baldocchi *et al.*, 2001; Keyser *et al.*, 2000). *GEP* flux analysis is of importance of studies concerning carbon assimilation efficiency at leaf, plant and ecosystem levels. However, due to the limitations of measurement methods, *GEP* cannot be directly measured *in situ*. State-of-the-art eddy covariance (EC) systems installed on flux towers make it possible to measure only the net fluxes of CO₂ (*NEP*) (Urbaniak *et al.*, 2016). *NEP* is defined as a balance of the processes of CO₂ exchange between the ecosystem and the atmosphere and is expressed as a difference between *GEP* and the total amount of CO₂ released by the ecosystem to the atmosphere (ecosystem respiration, R_{eco}) (Law *et al.*, 2002).

Remote sensing studies of global vegetation phenology started in 1979 when the meteorological satellite data of Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR) became available (Goward & Huemmrich, 1992). Since then, the following satellite missions (MODIS, LANDSAT, Sentinel-2) have been providing data which allow remote sensing-based estimation of *LAI*, fraction of PAR absorbed by plants (*fAPAR*) and *GEP* of biomes and ecosystems across the globe with higher spatial and temporal resolutions as well as higher accuracy (e.g., Running *et al.*, 2004; Gao *et al.*, 2017). Traditionally, *GEP* is estimated as a function of vegetation indices (*VI*) related to canopy greenness or based on models including in their formulation also Light Use Efficiency (*LUE*) and/or Photosynthetic Active Radiation (PAR) terms (e.g., Gitelson *et al.*, 2012; Rossini *et al.*, 2012; Sakowska *et al.*, 2014). Many studies have highlighted that simple greenness-related *VI*s can be successfully used for remote sensing-based estimation of *LAI* (e.g., Gitelson *et al.*, 2003), chlorophyll content (e.g., Gitelson *et al.*, 2005), *fAPAR* (Sims *et al.*, 2006), fractional vegetation cover (e.g., Glenn *et al.*, 2008) and *GEP* (e.g., Prince & Goward, 1995). Among these greenness indices, Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (*NDVI*) has been the most commonly applied, even though it tends to saturate under conditions of moderate- to high aboveground biomass (e.g., Gitelson, 2004). For this reason, a big effort was undertaken to develop new *NDVI*-type indices that would not only minimize the soil background influences (e.g., Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index, *SAVI*, Huete, 1988), but would also overcome the saturation problem in biophysical parameters estimation (Gitelson, 2004). According to existing studies, Modified Simple Ratio (*MSR*, Chen & Cihlar, 1996), Renormalized Difference Vegetation Index (*RDVI*, Roujean & Breon, 1995), Wide Dynamic Range Vegetation Index (*WDRVI*, Gitelson, 2004) or Enhanced Vegetation Index (*EVI* Huete *et al.*, 2002; Rahman *et al.*, 2005) are more linearly related to *fAPAR*, *LAI*, or *GEP* and they allow to estimate these biophysical parameters with higher accuracy. Due to the limited sensitivity of “greenness” indices to a short-term stress which may not impact the chlorophyll content, the Photochemical Reflectance Index (*PRI*) was introduced (Gamon, Penuelas & Field, 1992). *PRI* may be an indicator of the *LUE* in the process of photosynthesis (Gamon, Penuelas & Field, 1992; Goerner *et al.*, 2011; Penuelas, Filella & Gamon, 1995) and has been used in *GEP* and *LUE* estimations at leaf, plant and ecosystem levels (e.g., Rossini *et al.*, 2012; Cheng *et al.*, 2014; Gitelson, Gamon & Solovchenko, 2017).

Both the seasonal dynamics and relationships between *VI*s and biophysical parameters have been analyzed in numerous studies. The relationships of spectral data have been investigated in relation to *LAI* (Baret & Guyot, 1991; Law & Waring, 1994; Spanner et al., 1990; Zheng & Moskal, 2009), *fAPAR* (Asrar et al., 1984; Wang et al., 2004; Sakowska, Juszczak & Gianelle, 2016), and the CO_2 fluxes exchanged between the ecosystem and the atmosphere – particularly *GEP* (Rossini et al., 2012; Sakowska et al., 2014; Skinner, Wylie & Gilmanov, 2011; Uzdicka et al., 2017), *NEP* (Hassan, Bourque & Meng, 2006; Propastin & Kappas, 2009; Veroustraete, Patyn & Myneni, 1996) and *NPP* (Gower, Kucharik & Norman, 1999; Hunt, 1994; Paruelo et al., 1997; Ruimy, Saugier & Dedieu, 1994). These kind of relationships were mostly analyzed for individual ecosystems (e.g., grasslands - Rossini et al., 2012; Sakowska et al., 2014, peatlands - Chojnicki, 2013, savanna - Sjöström et al., 2009, forests - Xiao et al., 2004), or crop species on a separate basis (e.g., maize - Gitelson et al., 2003; Gitelson et al., 2014; Peng et al., 2011, maize and soybean - Gitelson et al., 2012, rice - Inoue et al., 2008, wheat - Wu et al., 2009).

In this paper we investigated the relationships between *LAI*, *VI*s and daily values of *GEP* determined using chamber measurements conducted on four crops grown in Poland. Similar kind of analyzes where *GEP* was correlated with *VI*s, *LAI* or chlorophyll content, and/or products of *VI*s and *PAR* have been presented in many studies (e.g., Rossini et al., 2012; Rossini et al., 2014; Sakowska et al., 2014; Gitelson et al., 2012; Gitelson et al., 2014). The relationships were investigated with an average midday *GEP* (e.g., Gitelson et al., 2006; Rossini et al., 2012; Sakowska et al., 2014) or with a daily sum of *GEP* (e.g., Rossini et al., 2012; Gitelson et al., 2014), but in all of these studies *GEP* was determined based on the ecosystem-scale EC measurements. In this study, *GEP* was obtained based on plot-scale chamber measurements. Although these measurements have some limitations (e.g., Urbaniak et al., 2016), the biggest advantage of chamber systems is that both *NEP* and *Reco* fluxes are measured directly and subsequently which facilitates the calculation of *GEP*.

In order to obtain remote sensing-based model which allows to estimate daily *GEP* of crops independently from the type of the crop and climatic conditions with reliable performance, we studied a 3-year dataset (2011–2013) consisting of spectral and biophysical data for two winter (wheat and rye) and two spring (barley, potato) crops. Our specific objectives were to test (1) the accuracy of daily *GEP* estimations with remote sensing-based models fed with different *VI*s and *VI*s**PAR* and a model based on *LAI*, and (2) whether the accuracy of *GEP* estimations increases when products of *VI* and *LAI* are included in the model. Besides, considering that for some crops the hysteresis of the relationships between *VI*s and biophysical parameters is observed (Peng et al., 2017), we aimed at developing a simple linear empirical model based on *VI*s and *LAI* in order to reduce hysteresis of the *VI*s vs. *GEP* relationships between vegetative and reproductive phases of crop development cycle and to increase the accuracy of daily *GEP* (GEP_d) estimations of croplands. According to our knowledge this is also the first study in which CO_2 fluxes measured with chambers are combined with both *LAI* and *VI*s.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Experimental site

Measurements were conducted at the Brody Experimental Station (52°26'N, 16°18'E) on plots of the long-term experiment that has been conducted since 1957 by the Department of Agronomy, Poznań University of Life Sciences, Poland ([Blecharczyk et al., 2016](#)). Crops were grown in the crop rotation and monoculture systems under 11 different fertilization regimes (no fertilization, manure, manure + NPK, NPK + Ca-CaO, NPK, NP, NK, PK, N, P, K). The measurements presented in this paper were performed on four crop species: potato (var. *Wineta*), spring barley (var. *Nadek*), winter wheat (var. *Turkis*) and winter rye (var. *Dankowskie Zlote*), grown in a seven-year rotation (potato → spring barley → winter triticale → 1- and 2-year alfalfa → winter wheat → winter rye). The investigated crops were fertilized with NPK (90 kg N ha⁻¹ a⁻¹, 60 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ a⁻¹, 120 kg K₂O ha⁻¹ a⁻¹) with an addition of Ca-CaO (1.5 Mg CaO ha⁻¹ a⁻¹) and grown in 6 × 11 m plots separated by 0.5 m wide bare soil stripe. The annual mean air temperature of the study area is 7.9 °C, while the annual precipitation sum is 571 mm (average for 1959–1999). The soils are classified as *Albic Luvisols* developed on loamy sands overlying loamy material ([Majchrzak et al., 2016](#)).

Chamber CO₂ fluxes and flux modelling

Measurements of CO₂ fluxes (*NEP*, *R_{eco}*) were taken using a closed dynamic portable chamber system, which consisted of a transparent and non-transparent chambers to measure *NEP* and *R_{eco}* fluxes, respectively ([Chojnicki et al., 2010](#); [Juszczak et al., 2013](#)). Measurements were made in two subplots for each crop. The transparent chamber was made of three mm-thick Plexiglas (Evonik Industries, Darmstadt, Germany), as this material has a high solar radiation transmittance (approximately 90%, [Acosta et al., 2017](#); [Hoffman et al., 2015](#)). The non-transparent chamber was made of three mm-thick white PVC to ensure dark conditions inside the chamber. The chambers had dimensions of 0.78 × 0.78 × 0.50 m and a total volume of 0.296 m³. In case of winter rye and winter wheat, the extensions of 0.5 m height were used (made of the same material) in order to adopt the height of chamber to the height of the canopy. During the measurements, chambers were placed on square PVC collars (0.75 × 0.75 m), inserted into the soil just after sowing. The insertion depth of the collars was 15 cm. The chambers were equipped with a set of computer fans (1.4 W; 1,500 rpm each) mixing the air and a vent to equilibrate pressure in the chamber headspace. The air temperature inside the chamber headspace was measured with a radiation-shielded thermistor (T-107; Campbell Scientific, Logan, UT, USA) at a height of 0.3 m, or 0.8 m for short and tall chambers, respectively ([Juszczak, Acosta & Olejnik, 2012](#); [Juszczak et al., 2013](#)). The CO₂ concentration changes in the chamber was measured using LI-820 gas analyzer (LI-COR Inc., Lincoln, NE, USA). The air was circulated between the chamber and the analyzer in a closed loop with the flow rate of 0.7 l min⁻¹. In order to keep the air temperature inside the chamber headspace stable, the transparent chamber was cooled with a passive system described in [Acosta et al. \(2017\)](#).

Chamber measurements were taken every 3–5 weeks throughout the entire year (including winter) on cloudless days from sunrise to late afternoon (*Uzdzička et al., 2017*). However, when any clouds appeared (usually in the afternoon) a particular attention was paid to perform measurements at stable PAR conditions. Overall, 37 chamber campaigns were conducted in the years 2011–2013. Measurements of *NEP* and R_{eco} were taken on each of the soil frames several times per day (from five to 12, depending on the daytime length). A single *NEP* measurement took 120 seconds, and the subsequent *NEP* measurement at the same plot was taken before the value of incoming *PAR* changed by more than $150 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. A single measurement of R_{eco} took 180 seconds and the succeeding measurements were taken before the soil temperature at the same plot changed by more than $0.5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The CO_2 flux (F) in $\mu\text{mols m}^{-2}$ per time unit (t) was calculated from the gas concentration change in the chamber headspace ($\frac{\Delta C}{\Delta t}$), the chamber volume (V) and the enclosed soil area (A) from the following equation (*Urbaniak et al., 2016*):

$$F = \frac{\Delta C}{\Delta t} \cdot \frac{V}{A \cdot M_v} \quad (1)$$

where M_v ($\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$) is the molar volume of air at a given chamber air temperature and pressure. The determination coefficient (r^2) was calculated for each single chamber closure time and if $r^2 < 0.8$, the fluxes were excluded from the analyzes. To ensure that good quality near-zero fluxes were not erroneously excluded by this criteria, all rejected fluxes were visually inspected.

Fluxes of *NEP*, R_{eco} and *GEP* for measurement days and periods between campaigns were calculated using a simple empirical model described by *Drösler (2005)* and farther elaborated by *Hoffman et al. (2015)*. For this purpose, for each day of measurements, the relationships between measured R_{eco} and temperature were established by fitting to the campaign-specific flux dataset the temperature dependent Arrhenius-type respiration model of *Lloyd & Taylor (1994)*. Using the parameters of this model, R_{eco} values at the time of the *NEP* measurements were estimated based on the measured temperatures (*Juszczak et al., 2013*). In the next step, based on such estimated R_{eco} and measured *NEP*, *GEP* was calculated according to the formula $GEP = NEP + R_{\text{eco}}$. Subsequently, the calculated *GEP* fluxes were correlated with measured *PAR*, fitting to the campaign-specific *GEP* dataset a rectangular hyperbolic light response Michaelis–Menten kinetic model (*Michaelis & Menten, 1913*). The R_{eco} and *GEP* model parameters were interpolated linearly for the periods between the campaigns with a 30-minute step, so that, based on the continuous time series of measured *PAR* and temperature (means for 30-minute periods), *GEP* and R_{eco} was calculated. *NEP* was calculated from the formula $NEP = GEP - R_{\text{eco}}$. Daily sums of *GEP* (so called daily *GEP* (GEP_d)) were calculated as a sum of all 30-minute *GEP* fluxes estimated for each day with the flux model in between sunrise to sunset.

Measurements of *LAI* and spectral characteristics of the crops

LAI and multispectral data were collected during the growing season, from March to October, at one- to two-week intervals. At the spring barley plots measurements started in the middle of April (after sowing), whereas in case of potatoes in the 2nd week of May

Table 1 Spectral vegetation indices calculated from ground-based spectroscopy and presented in this study.

Spectral vegetation index	Formulation	Reference
NDVI	$NDVI = \frac{\rho_{850} - \rho_{670}}{\rho_{850} + \rho_{670}}$	Rouse et al. (1973)
SAVI	$SAVI = \frac{\rho_{850} - \rho_{670}}{\rho_{850} + \rho_{670} + L} (1 + L)$	Huete (1988)
PRI	$PRI = \frac{\rho_{570} - \rho_{531}}{\rho_{570} + \rho_{531}}$	Gamon, Penuelas & Field (1992)
WDRVI	$WDRVI = \frac{\alpha * \rho_{850} - \rho_{670}}{\alpha * \rho_{850} + \rho_{670}}$	Gitelson (2004)

Notes.

ρ , reflectance at a given wavelength; NDVI, Normalized Difference Vegetation Index; SAVI, Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index; PRI, Photochemical Reflectance Index; WDRVI, Wide Dynamic Range Vegetation Index.

(after planting). Only the data collected in the period between April and the 2nd week of August (just after harvesting) was considered in the analyzes, hence we did not present nor analyzed data collected after sowing of winter crops and after harvest. The dates of the measurement campaigns were selected so that these measurements could overlap with chamber measurements of CO₂ exchange. However, when the weather conditions were not stable due to appearing clouds, the measurements were repeated on the first sunny day following the chamber measurements. 36 measurement campaigns were organized in the 3-year period (2011–2013). Spectral measurements were carried out only on sunny days, always around the solar noon (between 10:00–14:00). Measurements of LAI and reflectance were taken at each plot in three replications, always in the same locations.

LAI was measured by means of the SunScan system (Delta-T Devices, Cambridge, UK). The spectral characteristics of the surface of plant-covered plots were measured using two 4-channel SKR1850 sensors (SKYE Instruments Ltd., Llandrindod Wells, UK) mounted on a portable SKL908 device (Spectrosense2+). Incident and reflected radiation was recorded at central wavelengths of 531, 570, 670 and 850 nm with 10 nm bandwidths. Next, applying the methodology developed by SKYE instruments Ltd. (SpectroSense2+ Manual), vegetation indices (NDVI, SAVI and PRI) were calculated (Table 1) according to the formula:

$$VI = \frac{(Z \cdot R_{1r} \cdot Y) - (R_{2r} \cdot X)}{(Z \cdot R_{1r} \cdot Y) + (R_{2r} \cdot X)}$$

where VI is a vegetation index, Z is a ratio sensitivity of reflected $R_{1r}:R_{2r}$; X and Y are incident readings for R_{1i} and R_{2i} , respectively (in $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$), while R_{1r} and R_{2r} correspond to reflected signal readings for wavelengths R1 and R2 (in nanoamps). For NDVI and SAVI, R1 and R2 correspond to 850 nm and 670 nm wavelengths respectively, while for PRI they correspond to wavelengths 570 nm and 531 nm. To calculate SAVI, the above formula was modified according to equation provided in Table 1. Wide Dynamic Range Vegetation Index was calculated from NDVI from the equation: $WDRVI = [(\alpha + 1)NDVI + (\alpha - 1)] / [(\alpha - 1)NDVI + (\alpha + 1)]$, where $\alpha = 0.2$ (Vina & Gitelson, 2005). In order to express values of this VI in positive numbers, sWDRVI was calculated from equation ($sWDRVI = (WDRVI + 1)/2$).

Table 2 The models tested for GEP_d estimation in the present study.

Model	Model formulation
1	$GEP_d = a \cdot LAI + b$
2	$GEP_d = a \cdot VI + b$
3	$GEP_d = a \cdot (VI \cdot PAR_d) + b$
4	$GEP_d = a \cdot (VI \cdot LAI) + b$

Models for GEP estimations

Daily GEP (GEP_d) were estimated based on linear regressions assuming a direct linear relationship between GEP_d and LAI (model 1), GEP_d and VI s (model 2), GEP_d and a product of VI s and mean daily PAR calculated for the time between the sunrise and sunset $-PAR_d$ (model 3), as well as GEP_d and a product of VI s and LAI (model 4) (Table 2). All the models were tested based on the combined multi-year (2011–2013) dataset for each crop species separately, as well as for all cereals: winter wheat, winter rye and spring barley (i) and cereals and potatoes (ii) considered together in order to develop the general models for GEP_d estimations for croplands. The general models with the best goodness of fit were then tested for each crop independently.

Statistical analysis

Pearson's correlation analysis was used to test the significance of the relationships between GEP_d and (i) LAI ; (ii) VI s ($NDVI$, $SAVI$, $WDRVI$, PRI); (iii) VI s* PAR_d ; and (iv) VI s* LAI . Analyses were conducted for each crop independently and for the combined datasets of cereals, as well as for cereals and potatoes considered together.

Each of the four analyzed models' coefficients were found by fitting each model against GEP_d . Goodness of fit statistics (coefficient of determination, R^2 ; root means square error, $RMSE$ in $gCO_2-C\ m^{-2}d^{-1}$; and normalized root mean square error, $NRMSE$ in %) were computed to compare the performance of the models.

In order to determine if there are significant differences in relationships between GEP_d and VI s between the vegetative and reproductive phases of crop development, the two-sample t -test approach was applied. The differences between analyzed relationships were considered to be significant if p -value obtained from the test was lower than 0.05.

Due to limited number of data (n equals from 21 to 26, depending on the crop and VI), validation of the best performing general models developed based on the combined dataset for cereals and potatoes was conducted for each crop species separately by comparing GEP_d retrieved from chamber CO_2 fluxes with GEP_d estimated based on the spectral model individually for each crop.

RESULTS

The seasonal variations of meteorological conditions for the analyzed growing seasons are presented in Fig. 1. The seasonal mean air temperatures were 14.0 °C, 13.9 °C and 12.4 °C, while the sums of precipitation were 331 mm, 363 mm and 344 mm for the periods between 1st of March and 31st of August of 2011, 2012 and 2013, respectively. The

Figure 1 Monthly sums of precipitation and mean air temperatures in Brody for 2011–2013.

Full-size [DOI: 10.7717/peerj.5613/fig-1](https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.5613/fig-1)

highest amount of precipitation was recorded in July 2011 (179 mm), July 2012 (99 mm), and June 2013 (125 mm). It has to be highlighted that sums of precipitation in May and June of 2011 - the two most critical for the plant growth months - were nearly two-times smaller than during the same period of the two following years. Considering the long term climatological records for this region, 2011 and 2013 are considered as warm (with the mean annual temperatures of 9.4 °C and 8.7 °C, respectively) and dry years (507 mm and 503 mm, respectively), while 2012 was considered as a warm (with the mean annual temperature of 9.0 °C) and wet (592 mm) year (Uzdzička et al., 2017). During the growing period of the main crop (March–August) the average PAR_d was 659 (± 241), 664 (± 224) and 641 (± 223) $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ in 2011, 2012 and 2013, respectively, with the maximum values of 1,011–1,068 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ (Fig. 2A).

The seasonal variations of LAI and GEP_d for all analyzed years and crops are presented in Fig. 2. The maximum LAI (LAI_{max}) and GEP_d of winter crops were recorded in the first week of May in 2011 and the last week of May–beginning of June in 2012 and 2013. In case of spring barley the LAI and GEP_d peaks occurred during the last week of May in 2011 and 2012 and in mid-June in 2013. Maximum rates of GEP_d and LAI at potato plots were recorded in the 2nd week of June in 2013 and 3rd week of June in 2011 and 2012. Maximum values of GEP_d and LAI for winter wheat were observed nearly at the same time, with just a 2-week shift in 2011. The LAI_{max} was 2.7, 3.3, and 4.4 m^2m^{-2} for winter wheat; 2.9, 5.0, and 4.3 m^2m^{-2} for winter rye; 2.5, 4.0 and 4.0 m^2m^{-2} for spring barley and 1.8, 3.4 and 3.2 m^2m^{-2} for potato, in 2011, 2012 and 2013, respectively (Table 3). The comparison of LAI_{max} between the investigated years showed that for all the investigated crops LAI_{max} was lower in 2011 than in both 2012 and 2013. There were no differences in

Figure 2 Seasonal variations of mean daily PAR (PAR_d) at the study site and daily GEP (GEP_d ; circles) and LAI (triangles) for the analyzed crops in the years 2011–2013. (A) mean daily PAR; (B) refers to winter wheat; (C) winter rye; (D) spring barley and (E) potatoes. Shaded areas indicate periods when the main crop was present in the field (these periods were analyzed in this study).

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Table 3 Seasonal mean and maximum values of GEP_d , $NDVI$, $SAVI$, $sWDRVI$, PRI , canopy height (H_{canopy}) and fractional cover ($F\%$) for the analyzed crops in the growing periods of 2011, 2012 and 2013.

	Units	Winter wheat		Winter rye		Spring barley		Potatoes		
		mean	max.	mean	max.	mean	max.	mean	max.	
2011	GEP_d	$gCO_2-Cm^{-2} s^{-1}$	3.60(±3.4)	12.14	6.31(±4.3)	14.30	3.75(±2.7)	11.33	2.77(±3.1)	10.54
	LAI	$m^2 m^{-2}$	1.56(±0.7)	2.67	2.14(±0.6)	2.87	1.19(±1.0)	2.53	0.83(±0.8)	1.80
	H_{canopy}	m	0.41(±0.2)	0.78	0.78(±0.6)	1.50	0.22(±0.2)	0.62	0.15(±0.2)	0.55
	$F\%$	%	0.38(±0.2)	0.60	0.66(±0.2)	0.90	0.37(±0.3)	0.85	0.19(±0.3)	0.70
	$NDVI$	–	0.65(±0.2)	0.79	0.68(±0.2)	0.88	0.51(±0.3)	0.85	0.23(±0.3)	0.77
	$SAVI$	–	0.17(±0.1)	0.28	0.18(±0.1)	0.33	0.16(±0.1)	0.30	0.08(±0.1)	0.28
	$sWDRVI$	–	0.47(±0.2)	0.63	0.55(±0.2)	0.75	0.37(±0.2)	0.71	0.37(±0.2)	0.61
	PRI	–	-0.19(±0.02)	-0.18	-0.18(±0.02)	-0.15	-0.20(±0.02)	-0.17	-0.19(±0.01)	-0.18
2012	GEP_d	$gCO_2-Cm^{-2} s^{-1}$	7.24(±5.9)	20.33	8.78(±7.2)	31.65	5.78(±4.5)	14.36	6.31(±3.2)	12.66
	LAI	$m^2 m^{-2}$	1.73(±1.15)	3.33	3.12(±1.6)	5.00	2.05(±1.3)	4.03	1.84(±1.3)	3.37
	H_{canopy}	m	0.54(±0.4)	0.99	0.95(±0.6)	1.59	0.34(±0.3)	0.66	0.30(±0.3)	0.72
	$F\%$	%	0.41(±0.3)	0.80	0.75(±0.3)	0.95	0.56(±0.4)	0.95	0.39(±0.4)	0.95
	$NDVI$	–	0.48(±0.3)	0.84	0.56(±0.3)	0.90	0.44(±0.3)	0.84	0.55(±0.3)	0.88
	$SAVI$	–	0.15(±0.1)	0.31	0.18(±0.1)	0.31	0.17(±0.2)	0.38	0.22(±0.2)	0.49
	$sWDRVI$	–	0.39(±0.2)	0.70	0.49(±0.2)	0.79	0.35(±0.2)	0.69	0.46(±0.2)	0.77
	PRI	–	-0.19(±0.01)	-0.17	-0.20(±0.03)	-0.16	-0.22(±0.02)	-0.20	-0.20(±0.02)	-0.23
2013	GEP_d	$gCO_2-Cm^{-2} s^{-1}$	6.91(±6.3)	22.24	8.13(±6.3)	27.29	5.37(±4.2)	14.06	5.66(±3.6)	13.33
	LAI	$m^2 m^{-2}$	2.33(±1.8)	4.43	2.66(±1.8)	4.33	1.81(±1.5)	4.02	1.13(±1.2)	3.23
	H_{canopy}	m	0.38(±0.3)	0.82	0.80(±0.6)	1.40	0.28(±0.2)	0.60	0.24(±0.2)	0.45
	$F\%$	%	0.49(±0.4)	0.90	0.62(±0.3)	0.90	0.42(±0.4)	0.90	0.30(±0.2)	0.50
	$NDVI$	–	0.58(±0.4)	0.88	0.55(±0.3)	0.85	0.57(±0.3)	0.89	0.47(±0.3)	0.70
	$SAVI$	–	0.25(±0.2)	0.44	0.24(±0.1)	0.38	0.33(±0.1)	0.45	0.22(±0.1)	0.30
	$sWDRVI$	–	0.58(±0.2)	0.76	0.46(±0.2)	0.72	0.44(±0.2)	0.78	0.38(±0.2)	0.56
	PRI	–	-0.19(±0.03)	-0.17	-0.20(±0.03)	-0.16	-0.17(±0.1)	0.00	-0.20(±0.01)	-0.19

Notes.

For winter crops growing periods started on the 1st of March; for spring barley they started in the middle of April and lasted until skimming in the last week of August; for potato the growing seasons started in the second week of May and ended in the middle of September each year.

LAI_{max} for spring barley and potato in 2012 and 2013, while LAI_{max} was the highest for winter rye in 2012 and for winter wheat in 2013.

Similarly to LAI , the maximum daily GEP values of all the investigated crops were lower in 2011 compared to 2012 and 2013. The GEP_d of winter crops was 45% (winter rye) to 60% (winter wheat) lower in 2011 than in the two following years. The differences in maximum GEP_d of the spring crops (spring barley and potato) between 2011 and 2012, 2013 were smaller than in case of winter crops (20%). Maximum rates of GEP_d for winter wheat reached 12.1, 20.3 and 22.2 $gCO_2-Cm^{-2} d^{-1}$ and for winter rye 14.3, 31.6 and 27.3 $gCO_2-Cm^{-2} d^{-1}$ in 2011, 2012 and 2013, respectively, while for spring barley and potato GEP_d were 11.3 and 10.5 $gCO_2-Cm^{-2} d^{-1}$ in 2011, 14.4 and 12.3 $gCO_2-Cm^{-2} d^{-1}$ in 2012, and 14.0 and 13.3 $gCO_2-Cm^{-2} d^{-1}$ in 2013, respectively (Table 3).

Maximum values of $NDVI$ and $SAVI$ were observed nearly at the same time as the peaks of LAI and GEP_d (data shown in File S2). Moreover they were also lower in 2011 than in

the other two years, even though the observed differences in maximum VI s values were less prominent than the differences in the analyzed biophysical parameters (Table 3). All these data clearly indicate the effect of drought which occurred in the late spring - early summer of 2011, when sums of precipitation were 50% smaller than the precipitation observed in the same period of 2012 and 2013.

The analysis of linear regression revealed that LAI explained minimum 60% of the variability in GEP_d (Table 4). $NDVI$ and $SAVI$ explained from 52% to 72% of the variability in GEP_d for winter crops and up to 81%-91% for spring crops, when crops were considered separately. For crop-combined dataset, which consisted of the data of all the analyzed crops, $NDVI$ and $SAVI$ explained 50% to 65% of the variability in GEP_d . $SAVI$ -based models worked better only in case of models developed for winter rye, while in case of other crops it did not lead to more accurate estimations of GEP_d . Moreover, the $SAVI$ -based models ($R^2 = 0.50$, $NRMSE = 18.24\%$) developed for all the crops together were less accurate than $NDVI$ -based models ($R^2 = 0.65$, $NRMSE = 15.29\%$). The $sWDRVI$, which was expected to be more linearly correlated with GEP_d , explained between 50% (winter rye) to 86% (spring barley) of the GEP_d variability and did not improve the accuracy of GEP_d estimations in the crop-combined model ($R^2 = 0.65$, $NRMSE = 15.60\%$). The highest accuracy of model 2 was obtained for potato (if based on $NDVI$; $R^2 = 0.91$, $NRMSE = 10.94\%$). Inclusion of PAR_d into model 3 did not improve estimations of GEP_d for any of the investigated crops nor for the crop-combined datasets.

The inclusion of LAI into the “ VI s”-based models resulted in a general increase of their performance in case of the winter crops (Table 4). The highest increase of the accuracy of GEP_d estimations was found for $NDVI$ -based models. For winter wheat, $RMSE$ decreased from 4.31 to 3.56 $gCO_2-C m^{-2} d^{-1}$, while $NRMSE$ decreased from 19.83% to 16.38% after inclusion of LAI into $NDVI$ -based model. For winter rye, the changes were even more prominent - $RMSE$ decreased from 4.72 to 3.14 $gCO_2-C m^{-2} d^{-1}$, whereas $NRMSE$ decreased from 20.15% to 13.42%. Inclusion of LAI into $NDVI$ -based models developed for spring barley and potatoes led to a decrease of the accuracy of GEP_d estimations (Table 4). For spring barley $RMSE$ and $NRMSE$ increased from 1.73 to 1.79 $gCO_2-C m^{-2} d^{-1}$ and from 12.33% to 12.70%, respectively. The highest reduction of the model accuracy was observed for potatoes - $RMSE$ and $NRMSE$ increased from 1.26 to 2.10 $gCO_2-C m^{-2} d^{-1}$ and from 10.94% to 18.30%, respectively.

For more general models developed for the cereals and crop-combined datasets the inclusion of LAI into the VI s-based models also resulted in an improvement of model performance. $RMSE$ and $NRMSE$ of $NDVI$ and LAI -based models were the smallest and decreased from 4.09 to 3.42 $gCO_2-C m^{-2} d^{-1}$ and from 17.02% to 14.39% for cereals-combined models, and from 3.67 to 3.26 $gCO_2-C m^{-2} d^{-1}$ and from 15.29% to 13.57% for crop-combined datasets, respectively (Table 4). That is why we used the most general and the best fitting $NDVI*LAI$ model developed for all the crops together (cereals & potatoes, Fig. 3) to estimate GEP_d values for each crop separately (Fig. 4). Although there is a good agreement between observed and predicted GEP_d values for all the crops (Fig. 3), GEP_d estimated for winter crops and potatoes was underestimated, while GEP_d of spring barley was overestimated, but the rate of over- or under-estimation did not exceed 25% (Fig. 4).

Table 4 Summary of the statistics of linear regressions between LAI, VIs and GEP_d for each crop individually, for all cereals (winter and spring crops) and for cereals and potato grouped together.

Model		Winter wheat					Winter rye				
		<i>n</i>	R^2	<i>RMSE</i>	<i>NRMSE</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>n</i>	R^2	<i>RMSE</i>	<i>NRMSE</i>	<i>p</i>
		–	–	gCO ₂ -C m ⁻² s ⁻¹	%	–	–	gCO ₂ -C m ⁻² s ⁻¹	%	–	
1	LAI	26	0.62	4.07	18.75	<0.0001	26	0.60	4.34	18.54	<0.0001
	NDVI	25	0.56	4.31	19.83	<0.0001	26	0.52	4.72	20.15	<0.0001
2	SAVI	21	0.59	3.93	18.56	<0.0001	24	0.72	3.53	15.07	<0.0001
	sWDRVI	25	0.62	4.03	18.54	<0.0001	26	0.50	4.84	20.67	<0.0001
	PRI	22	0.49	4.64	19.79	<0.001	21	0.49	4.63	19.79	<0.0001
3	NDVI*PAR _d	25	0.54	4.40	20.24	<0.0001	26	0.59	4.39	18.76	<0.0001
	SAVI*PAR _d	21	0.52	4.29	20.25	<0.0001	24	0.57	4.38	18.73	<0.0001
	sWDRVI*PAR _d	25	0.59	4.21	19.40	<0.0001	26	0.58	4.41	18.85	<0.0001
4	NDVI*LAI	25	0.70	3.56	16.38	<0.0001	26	0.79	3.14	13.42	<0.0001
	SAVI*LAI	21	0.63	3.81	17.67	<0.0001	24	0.80	3.01	12.86	<0.0001
	sWDRVI*LAI	25	0.69	3.61	16.61	<0.0001	26	0.73	3.55	15.16	<0.0001
Spring barley						Potatoes					
1	LAI	22	0.65	2.51	17.87	<0.0001	22	0.75	2.18	18.99	<0.0001
	NDVI	25	0.82	1.73	12.33	<0.0001	22	0.91	1.26	10.94	<0.0001
2	SAVI	23	0.81	1.77	12.63	<0.0001	19	0.90	1.40	12.21	<0.0001
	sWDRVI	25	0.86	1.55	10.99	<0.0001	22	0.85	1.66	14.45	<0.0001
	PRI	21	0.05	3.88	27.24	0.235	21	0.03	4.22	36.75	0.4533
3	NDVI*PAR _d	25	0.82	1.70	12.12	<0.0001	22	0.86	1.54	13.43	<0.0001
	SAVI*PAR _d	23	0.83	1.66	11.81	<0.0001	19	0.81	1.64	14.26	<0.0001
	sWDRVI*PAR _d	25	0.84	1.64	11.69	<0.0001	22	0.79	1.87	16.25	<0.0001
4	NDVI*LAI	22	0.83	1.79	12.70	<0.0001	22	0.76	2.10	18.30	<0.0001
	SAVI*LAI	22	0.78	1.92	13.67	<0.0001	22	0.76	1.99	17.30	<0.0001
	sWDRVI*LAI	22	0.81	1.73	12.80	<0.0001	22	0.75	2.12	18.49	<0.0001
ALL cereals						Cereals + potatoes					
1	LAI	74	0.61	4.10	17.09	<0.0001	96	0.65	3.79	15.81	<0.0001
	NDVI	76	0.60	4.09	17.02	<0.0001	98	0.65	3.67	15.29	<0.0001
2	SAVI	68	0.54	4.34	18.09	<0.0001	87	0.50	4.38	18.24	<0.0001
	sWDRVI	76	0.62	4.03	16.79	<0.0001	98	0.65	3.74	15.60	<0.0001
	PRI	64	0.37	4.86	20.26	<0.0001	85	0.29	4.98	20.73	<0.0001
3	NDVI*PAR _d	76	0.59	4.10	17.10	<0.0001	98	0.61	3.79	15.79	<0.0001
	SAVI*PAR _d	68	0.48	4.61	19.19	<0.0001	87	0.39	4.76	19.85	<0.0001
	sWDRVI*PAR _d	76	0.58	4.15	17.30	<0.0001	98	0.59	3.88	16.16	<0.0001
4	NDVI*LAI	73	0.74	3.42	14.39	<0.0001	95	0.74	3.26	13.57	<0.0001
	SAVI*LAI	67	0.63	3.87	16.12	<0.0001	89	0.56	4.03	16.79	<0.0001
	sWDRVI*LAI	73	0.65	3.88	16.18	<0.0001	99	0.71	3.40	14.16	<0.0001

Notes.

n, number of observations; R^2 , coefficient of determination; *RMSE*, root mean square error; *NRMSE*, normalized root mean square error. The best performing models are in bold print.

Figure 3 Scatterplots of relationships between (A) $NDVI * LAI$ and GEP_d and (B) observed and predicted GEP_d estimated for all the crops considered together, based on the general crop-combined model.

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DISCUSSION

Most of the remote sensing-based models to estimate GEP of croplands are rather crop-specific. They were developed for maize, soybean (Gitelson *et al.*, 2012), rice (Inoue *et al.*, 2008), wheat (Wu *et al.*, 2009), rye, barley, potato (Uzdicka *et al.*, 2017) and in the majority of studies it has not been tested if these models can be directly applied (without reparametrization) for estimation of CO₂ uptake for other crops. Here we presented a more general and robust approach based on combining the datasets for the two winter and two spring crops together and we proved that the accuracy of crop-combined models is not different from those developed for winter crops on a separate basis (NRMSE of the best crop-combined models are in range of 13–16%), but it may be lowered compared to simple VI -based models developed for spring barley and potato (NRMSE is in range of about 11% for spring crops, whereas NRMSE of the best crop-combined model is 13.57%, Table 4).

The weakness of our study is related to the applied method for spectral properties measurements. The Spectrosense 2+ measuring system with 4-channel upward- and downward-looking multispectral radiometers allows to measure incident and reflected radiation only in four most commonly used bands (NIR, RED and GREEN wavelengths). Due to missing measurements at red-edge, blue and other specific wavelengths we were not able to calculate many other important indices more sensitive to medium to high biomass (e.g., $NDVI_{red-edge}$ (Gitelson & Merzlyak, 1994), Normalized Difference Structural Index, $NDSI$ (Vescovo *et al.*, 2012)) or EVI (Huete *et al.*, 2002), which could help to overcome the saturation effect of classical greenness indices. Besides $NDVI$, which tends to saturate asymptotically under moderate-to-high biomass conditions (Huete *et al.*, 2002; Gitelson *et al.*, 2003), we analyzed $SAVI$ —the index developed to compensate for the reflectance

Figure 4 Scatter plots of relationships between observed and predicted GEP_d for the analyzed crops. (A) winter wheat; (B) winter rye; (C) spring barley and (D) potatoes. GEP_d for each crop was estimated based on the general crop-combined model: $GEP_d = 4.87 * (NDVI * LAI) + 0.61$.

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from soil (Huete, 1988), and WDRVI which was developed to increase the linearity with biophysical parameters (Gitelson, 2004). SAVI improved the accuracy of GEP_d estimations only for winter rye (NRMSE of SAVI model was smaller by 33% than for NDVI-based model), but did not improve the accuracy of GEP_d estimations of neither winter wheat nor spring crops. WDRVI improved estimations of GEP_d only for spring barley (NRMSE of WDRVI model was smaller by 16% than for NDVI-based model), and did not affect the GEP_d model accuracy of other crops (Table 4). WDRVI explained maximum 62% of GEP_d variability for winter rye and only 50% for winter wheat and RMSE in both cases was not very much different from NDVI- or SAVI- based models. In case of spring crops WDRVI performed much better and explained around 85–86% of variability in GEP_d for spring barley and potato, respectively, although only for spring barley this index was the

Figure 5 Relationships between the best fitted VIs and GEP_d as well as between observed and predicted daily GEP for spring barley (A, B) and potatoes (C, D). Predicted GEP_d was calculated based on VI model resulting in the best goodness of fit (see Table 4).

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best proxy of GEP_d (Table 4, Fig. 5). NDVI explained even 91% of GEP_d variability of potato being the best predictor of GEP_d .

Inclusion of PAR into VI-based models, although successfully implemented in many studies (e.g., Gitelson et al., 2006; Wu et al., 2009; Rossini et al., 2010), did not improve goodness-of-fit of the linear regressions for any of the crops. Similar results have been reported also by Rossini et al. (2012) and Sakowska et al. (2014) for alpine grassland ecosystems. Sakowska et al. (2014) hypothesized that this might be the result of a different response of plant photosynthesis to direct and diffuse radiation, but this cannot support our results, because all measurements were taken under sunny days. As stated by Rossini et al. (2012), although models including PAR and VI take into account variations related

to changing incident radiation, they may not improve estimation of GEP_d due to higher light use efficiency (LUE) of plants at lower values of incident PAR and lower LUE at higher PAR (due to higher photoinhibition). [Rossini et al. \(2012\)](#) argued that higher photosynthetic efficiency at low PAR may be the result of two processes: (1) more diffuse light is penetrating more deep into the canopy, and (2) less photoinhibition on the top of the canopy which may reduce tendency towards saturation ([Chen, Shen & Kato, 2009](#)). It is well known that exposure of photosynthetic machinery of plants to strong light may result in inhibition of the photosystem II (PSII) activity, due to toxic effect of reactive oxygen species ([Murata et al., 2007](#)). Although this effect may be overcome by rapid and efficient repair of PSII ([Aro, Virgin & Anderson, 1993](#)), environmental factors, such as e.g., heat stress, which often occur during growing season, may inhibit the reparation of PSII and hence reduce efficiency of CO_2 uptake ([Murata et al., 2007](#)). This is probably why we observed a very weak correlation between GEP_d and average daily values of incident PAR ([Fig. 6](#)). Although GEP_d was increasing with increasing PAR during the vegetative phase of crop development, LUE became stable, while LAI and biomass of plants have been increasing continuously ([Figs. 2 and 6](#)). During the reproductive phase, both GEP_d and LUE decreased with decreasing values of PAR_d , but this effect is clearly related to progressive degradation of photosynthetic apparatus towards the senescence. Considering the above, we may hypothesize that the increasing GEP_d observed during the vegetative phase of plant development cycle is mostly related to increasing biomass of plants and amount of photosynthetic apparatus rather than to increasing PAR. Another point is that the chamber measurements of CO_2 fluxes were taken on sunny days, when PAR was not a limiting factor for GEP . This is probably why we found a weak correlation between GEP_d and average daily PAR, which can indicate that over such a long seasonal time scales PAR is not the most relevant determinant of GEP_d , although in shorter time-scales it may be more important (as indicated also by [Sims et al., 2006](#)).

One of the possible explanation, why the simple greenness indices considered in this study were moderately correlated with GEP_d of winter crops might be that we considered all the 3-years period dataset together for all the crops, while it is clear that climatological conditions for all these years were extremely different. Especially, 2011- a year with a very dry spring, has disturbed the relationships between GEP_d and VI s (mainly for winter crops) and although not shown, the same VI s-based models obtained specifically for 2012 and 2013 resulted in a much higher accuracy. However, our intention was to test the multiyear relationships between VI s and GEP_d in order to develop more general models which can be applied to years characterized by different climatological conditions, still maintaining a reliable performance.

Another reason for higher uncertainties of GEP_d estimations with VI s, observed specifically for winter crops, might be related to seasonal changes in canopy structure and biochemical traits which may modify the spectral response of plants over the growing season at different phenological phases of plant development ([Asrar et al., 1984](#); [Asrar, Kanemasu & Yoshida, 1985](#); [Peng et al., 2017](#)). The seasonal courses of GEP_d and $NDVI$ are nearly the same and are overlapping for potato ([Fig. 7](#)) and that is why the greenness indices ($NDVI$, $SAVI$ and $WDRVI$) are good proxies of GEP_d for this crop (R^2 for GEP_d vs. VI s

Figure 6 Scatterplots of relationships between average daily PAR (PAR_d) and GEP_d (A) as well as PAR_d and LUE (B) for vegetative and reproductive phases of plant development. Data for all the crops are presented on the graphs.

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relationships of 0.85, 0.90 and 0.91 for $WDRVI$, $SAVI$ and $NDVI$ respectively, see Table 4). However, in case of winter crops and spring barley these GEP_d and $NDVI$ seasonal courses did not correspond as well as they did for potato. We observed clearly a shift in seasonal courses of $NDVI$ and GEP_d for spring barley, winter rye and winter wheat, and peaks of $NDVI$ occurred earlier than peaks of GEP_d for all these crops (Fig. 7). It is well known that $NDVI$ saturates at moderate-to-high biomass conditions (Gitelson et al., 2003), but this effect seems to be crop specific and may depend on the structure of the crop canopy. In spring barley $NDVI$ was increasing together with LAI and GEP_d until DOY140 (Fig. 7). After this day $NDVI$ saturated and stabilized at around 0.8 until DOY165, although GEP_d and LAI were already decreasing. For winter wheat, $NDVI$ also followed LAI development during the vegetative phase (until DOY140), but until DOY120 the increase rates of $NDVI$ were slower and its value did not exceed 0.4 since the beginning of the growing season, while GEP_d increased much faster during this period. Hence, we can hypothesize that GEP_d vs. $NDVI$ relationships might be different in the period between DOY80 to DOY120 and between DOY120 to DOY140, although we cannot confirm this due to not sufficient amount of data. After DOY140, $NDVI$ saturated and stabilized again at around 0.8 until DOY165 and just after it begun to decrease slowly and the rate of decreasing was the same as the rate of GEP_d decrease. Hence, in the reproductive/senescence phase of wheat development from DOY165 till the harvest, again GEP_d vs. $NDVI$ relationships were significantly ($p < 0.05$) different (Fig. 8). Much more complex analysis are related to winter rye, where $NDVI$ reached maximum values of around 0.9 very soon after the beginning of the analyzed period and was quite stable until DOY140, although LAI and GEP_d were continuously increasing until DOY145. When analyzing the winter crop data, specifically winter rye, one should take into account that this crop is sown in the late September under

Figure 7 Example of seasonal courses of GEP_d , NDVI, LAI and NDVI*LAI for winter wheat (A), winter rye (B), spring barley (C) and potato (D) in 2012. Note: scales are different.

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Figure 8 Scatterplots of relationships between NDVI and GEP_d as well as between $NDVI \cdot LAI$ and GEP_d for the analyzed crops. (A and B) winter rye; (C and D) winter wheat; (E and F) spring barley; and (G and H) potato. Relationships are determined for vegetative and reproductive phases of plant development cycle.

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the climatic conditions of the Central Europe and during warm winters it can continue to grow. In early spring, after the beginning of the growing period, the canopy of the crop may get very dense and green if it is growing under non N-limited conditions. In our case, the winter of 2012 was warmer than in 2011 and 2013, with a very warm December and January 2012 (Fig. 1), hence crops continued to grow during this time. Considering above, this may explain why *NDVI* saturated already in the late March/beginning of April 2012 at winter rye fields (Fig. 7). In 2011 and 2013 this effect was also observed, but beginning of the period when *NDVI* started to saturate occurred one month later (in April), due to longer and colder winters. For the first part of the growing season of 2012 for the winter rye, *NDVI* was not sensitive to changes neither in biomass, nor in GEP_d (the same was observed in all the three analyzed years, data shown in (File S7)). Between DOY160 and the harvest, changes of *NDVI* followed changes of GEP_d , but again the GEP_d vs. *NDVI* relationships were significantly ($p < 0.05$) different than those found for vegetative phase (Fig. 8).

Similar kind of hysteresis were found in relationships between GEP_d and *LAI* and GEP_d vs. chlorophyll content in maize by Gitelson *et al.* (2014), as well as between reflectance in red and blue bands and greenness indices (e.g., *NDVI*) vs. chlorophyll content in maize and soybean by Peng *et al.* (2017). The relationships between these variables were significantly different for vegetative and reproductive phases of maize and soybean development. In our study we found similar kind of differences between GEP_d and *NDVI* in both analyzed winter crops, but not in spring barley and potato. Each of the crops has different height, *LAI*, canopy architecture, and different contribution of soil to canopy reflectance. As already indicated e.g., by Gausman *et al.* (1971) and Gausman, Rodriguez & Richardson (1976), and discussed by Peng *et al.* (2017), optical properties of leaf and canopies are greatly impacted by leaf structure and canopy architecture and that is why relationships between biophysical properties of crops and *VI*s are often different at different phenological phases of plant development (Asrar *et al.*, 1984; Asrar, Kanemasu & Yoshida, 1985; Gitelson *et al.*, 2014). In winter crops the canopy is very green, dense and more “closed” at the beginning of the growing season and hence reflectance from soil is minimized, while absorption in the red part of the spectrum is high. That is why *NDVI* saturates early in the season and it does not change much over the vegetative phase of crop development. Whereas in the reproductive/senescence phases, when the leaf structure and canopy architecture change and chlorophyll content is reduced, more light can penetrate deeper into the canopy and that is why the soil reflectance contribution is also higher. Due to differences in canopy architecture and leaf structure and different patterns of light absorption and reflectance by crops as well as different contribution of soil into overall reflectance of vegetation canopies at different phases of phenological development of plants, the relationships between GEP_d and *VI*s of winter crops are different for vegetative and reproductive phases, as indicated also by (Peng *et al.*, 2017; Gitelson *et al.*, 2014). In potato, canopy is more open since the beginning of the growing season, and soil reflectance contributes significantly to the overall canopy reflectance. With the development of the green biomass, absorption of the red part of the spectrum is increasing, while soil contribution is decreasing. After the peak of biomass, during the reproductive and senescence phases, when chlorophyll pigments are

degrading while leaves are folding, more light penetrates deeper to the canopy and again contribution of the soil reflectance to the overall canopy reflectance increases, whereas absorption in the red part of the spectrum decreases. Probably this effect can cause lack of hysteresis in GEP_d vs. $NDVI$ relationships for this crop, as the slopes of curves for this relationships in both phases of potato development are the same (Fig. 8).

In winter crops, LAI started to increase since the beginning of the growing season throughout the vegetative phase and GEP_d followed changes in the crop biomass, although $NDVI$ was already not sensitive enough to track changes in photosynthesis. The same LAI development was found in spring barley and potato, however $NDVI$ followed changes in LAI and as discussed above, it was sensitive enough to track changes in GEP_d of spring crops. After the peak of biomass, LAI of all the crops decreased slightly and stabilized at around $2\text{--}3\text{ m}^2\text{ m}^{-2}$ until the harvest (note, we are not investigating *greenLAI*, but total LAI). This led to the conclusion, that LAI can be successfully used to overcome problems with greenness indices, which seem to saturate very early in the growing season in winter crops. By multiplication of $NDVI$ -based VI s by LAI this specific issue of seasonal GEP_d vs. VI s relationships can be overcome and model uncertainties can be reduced (see Table 4). The curves presenting the seasonal variations of the $NDVI*LAI$ product are more closely related to seasonal changes in GEP_d (Fig. 7) and this effect is not only restricted to winter crops, but can also be observed in case of spring crops. For both winter crops the slopes of the GEP_d vs. $NDVI$ relationships are significantly different ($p < 0.05$) between vegetative and reproductive phases and between the species, which can limit their application for accurate estimation of GEP_d of these canopies over the entire season (Fig. 8). However, after multiplying $NDVI$ by LAI slopes for the same relationships are much closer to each other (Fig. 8), and uncertainties of GEP_d estimations are lower, as indicated in Table 4. Moreover, this approach does not change significantly slopes of the GEP_d vs. $NDVI$ relationships for spring crops (Fig. 8), although uncertainties of GEP_d estimations for potato can be higher (Table 4).

However, in the more general, crop-combined dataset representing both winter and spring crops, the multiplication of $NDVI$ and LAI led to an improvement of GEP_d estimations (Table 4). NRMSE for the model fed with $NDVI*LAI$ was about 14%, and it explained around 74% of GEP_d variability independently from the crop species. The obtained accuracy is in the range which can promote this approach in remote sensing studies in order to overcome the hysteresis of GEP_d vs. VI s relationship between vegetative and reproductive phases, which indeed may limit their applicability to predict photosynthesis of different crops over the entire growing season.

The limitation of this approach is that VI s are the remote sensing source of information which can be obtained from space, while space born products of LAI are result of (1) statistical models which quantify the relationships between LAI and canopy reflectance or VI s (Baret & Guyot, 1991; Verrelst et al., 2015; Linker & Gitelson, 2017), or (2) different radiative transfer models (Baret et al., 2007; Richter et al., 2012). These relationships between LAI and VI s are often canopy structure- and land-cover depended and are highly impacted by leaf angle distribution, vegetation clumping, optical properties of leaf and canopies (Goward & Huemmrich, 1992). What is more, different canopies may exhibit large

variations in reflectance properties which can result in different values of VIs for similar values of LAI and other biophysical parameters (Pinty, Leprieur & Verstraete, 1993). There are few satellite based products of LAI (Zheng & Moskal, 2009) which are based not only on single vegetation indices such as EVI (Huete et al., 2002) or Reduced Simple Ratio (RSR , Brown et al., 2000), but also on linear or non-linear models including many vegetation indices which are used to estimate and map LAI at the landscape and global levels with Landsat satellites (Cohen, Maerspergerr & Tumer, 2003). Hence, we believe that this kind of data (LAI retrieved from space borne data) can also be used to mitigate the hysteresis effect described above and increase the accuracy of GEP_d estimations for croplands. We can even speculate, considering that $greenLAI$ and total LAI analyzed in this study are the same in the vegetative phase of plant development, while $greenLAI$ is decreasing till “zero” in the senescence phase, although the total LAI remains relatively constant during this phase, that the product of $NDVI$ and $greenLAI$ retrieved from satellite data will improve estimations of GEP_d of winter crops even better than total LAI used in this study. $GreenLAI$ multiplied by greenness related VIs shall improve model accuracy both in the vegetative and reproductive phases of plant development cycle, due to reasons described above. Hence, we hypothesize that the overall hysteresis effect observed in relationships between greenness related VIs and GEP will be reduced. However, this effect will need to be studied in the future in more detail with the application of both $greenLAI$ estimated at the ground and based on satellites data.

The proposed approach and empirical models developed in this study can be tested in other regions and for other C3 crops in order to verify the validity of our assumptions. Considering that our models were developed based on four different crops and three years characterized by different climatic conditions we believe that application of the proposed approaches and formulas can result in reliable estimation of daily GEP values of crops also for other regions with similar climate and crop management systems.

CONCLUSIONS

The analyzed multiyear relationships between GEP_d and VIs showed that only in the case of spring crops GEP_d can be estimated with a high accuracy and with an error smaller than 12% based on simple greenness indices ($NDVI$, $SAVI$, $WDRVI$). The same kind of analyzes conducted for winter crops are much less accurate, and the error of GEP_d estimation is higher than 18%.

The reason for the weaker correlation between daily GEP and VIs of winter crops may be related to hysteresis effect of this relationship found between the vegetative and reproductive phases of plant development cycle. We found that multiplication of greenness indices by LAI (which is much more sensitive to changes in biomass and GEP_d of winter crops, specifically during the vegetative phase of their development) can mitigate such effect. The product of multiplication of LAI and VI has in most cases the same seasonality as GEP_d and that is why it represents well the seasonal changes of gross CO_2 fluxes of croplands.

In order to propose as universal model as possible, we investigated the relationships between VIs and GEP_d for the cereals- and crop-combined datasets, where both winter

and spring crops, as well as cereals and potato were included. We found that there is no difference in GEP_d estimations between these two kind of approaches and this general model based on approach where $NDVI$ is multiplied by LAI , can be successfully applied for both winter and spring crops as well as for cereals and potato, while the error of this estimation is not higher than 14%. However, this approach underestimated GEP_d of winter crops and potatoes, and overestimated GEP_d of spring barley, but the rate of over-or under-estimations was not higher than 25%.

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Competing Interests

The authors declare there are no competing interests.

Author Contributions

- Radosław Juszczak conceived and designed the experiments, performed the experiments, analyzed the data, contributed reagents/materials/analysis tools, prepared figures and/or tables, authored or reviewed drafts of the paper, approved the final draft.
- Bogna Uździcka performed the experiments, analyzed the data, contributed reagents/materials/analysis tools, prepared figures and/or tables, authored or reviewed drafts of the paper.
- Marcin Stróżecki performed the experiments, approved the final draft.
- Karolina Sakowska performed the experiments, authored or reviewed drafts of the paper, approved the final draft.

Data Availability

The following information was supplied regarding data availability:

The raw data are provided in the [Supplemental Files](#).

Supplemental Information

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